

ISic3381

I.Sicily inscription 3381

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

limestone

Object

funerary

monument

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

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Autopsy

2013.10.03

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Syracusae

Place of origin (modern)

Siracusa

Provenance

necropolis of contrada Canalicchio ('found by Orsi in a field, c.1 km from the excavation, 'al bivio della rotabile per Florida e per Belvedere', at limits of

necropolis

Coordinates

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Siracusa, Museo Archeologico
Regionale Paolo Orsi, inventory 39798

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 645609

Bibliography

undefined, undefined, undefined, undefined, undefined, undefined 1876-.

Notizie degli scavi di antichità. *Notizie degli scavi di antichità*. At 325-326
Libertini, G 1929. Il regio museo archeologico di Siracusa. *Guide dei musei
italiani*. Roma. At 123

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